

Building sustainable and impactful tools: best practices and future directions for geo-dashboards

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Summary

Web-based geographic visualization systems – geo-dashboards for short – are increasingly used in geography and urban studies, serving as both communication tools and decision support systems. However, cohesive and reusable approaches to creating these systems remain scarce and thus the current landscape of geo-dashboards is relatively fragmented. In addition, they are often developed in an ad-hoc fashion, which hinders their impact and longevity. To help address these challenges, we review the state-of-the-art academic literature on the use and development of dashboards across geo-related disciplines and, based on a systematic literature review of 82 geo-dashboard articles, identify key issues around stakeholder engagement, longevity, accessibility, and impact. Drawing on the current state-of-the-art, we propose an agenda for building more sustainable, accessible and impactful geo-dashboards.

KEYWORDS: dashboards, geovisualization, open-source software, systematic review

1. Introduction

Web technologies have transformed geo-visualization from niche desktop applications to online, interactive visual systems. These systems – referred to here as geo-dashboards – can combine geographic and non-geographic data through interactive, multi-view displays (Kitchin and McArdle, 2016), enabling users to explore multiple perspectives on the same topic simultaneously (Sarıkaya et al., 2019). Geo-dashboards can reach many, large audiences and serve both general communication (e.g. COVID-19 dashboards) and more specialized decision-making support purposes (e.g. planning support systems).

Geo-dashboards are increasingly developed and used within geography and urban studies (Praharaj et al., 2023). However, despite their potential, the current landscape of geo-dashboards is in its infancy and relatively fragmented. This lack of cohesion is evident in the absence of unified frameworks or broadly agreed-upon best practices, which we do find in the related, more mature sub-disciplines of GIScience and geographic data science. This fragmented state leads to inefficiencies such as duplication in software development, uneven maintenance, limited accessibility, and – all too often – eventual obsolescence of tools. Without a more structured approach, the sustainability and impact of geo-dashboards are at risk. Furthermore, many geo-dashboards do not fully consider actual user needs, diminishing their practical utility and long-term reuse. To address these challenges, we review the academic literature on the state-of-the-art use and development of dashboards across geo-related disciplines and, based on a structured literature review of 82 geo-dashboard articles, identify key issues around stakeholder engagement, longevity, accessibility, and impact. Based on this analysis of the state-

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of-the-art, we propose an agenda for building more sustainable, accessible and impactful geo-dashboards.

2. Current State-of-the-art in Geo-dashboards

We identified relevant papers in Scopus using specific keyword combinations focused on *dashboards* or *platforms* within *geography* and *urban studies* (Figure 1). Two reviewers manually conducted the screening of 2,626 potentially relevant papers, assisted by the machine learning-based software ASReview to improve efficiency (Van de Schoot et al., 2021).

Figure 1 Literature screening process and selection criteria

The 82 papers were then analyzed using a framework that divides the development of a geo-dashboard into three phases: input, actual development, and outcomes (shown in **Figure 2**). As stakeholder engagement is critical in creating more sustainable geo-dashboards, we highlight it as a separate dimension in our analysis. This extended abstract primarily focuses on the dimensions of *outcomes* and *stakeholder engagement*.

Figure 2 Three key phases and elements of the geo-dashboard development process

2.1. Outcomes: Accessibility, Longevity, and Abandonware

Within the outcome phase, we analyzed the 82 geo-dashboards across several dimensions, beginning with an evaluation of the availability and accessibility of links to their platforms or code repositories. We verified whether each tool provided a link to both the tool itself and its corresponding code repository, and we checked if these links remained accessible after publication.

The current state of geo-dashboards highlights significant gaps that hinder their impact and sustainability. Of the tools we reviewed, only 24% of the tools we reviewed provided valid links to their platforms or code repositories, while 16% shared links that became invalid after publication, and 60% lacked source code links altogether. Even tools that are accessible and open source often fail to gain visibility within the research community, as repositories frequently attract minimal engagement, such as ‘forks’ or ‘likes’ on GitHub. This lack of discovery and reuse limits their potential for meaningful and lasting impact. As many geo-dashboards seem to be developed once, then published about, and not maintained or used afterwards they can be characterized as abandonware.

As such, our review identifies *long-term accessibility* and *longevity* of tools as two of the most critical challenges facing geo-dashboards. Many tools become inaccessible shortly after publication. Although developers frequently emphasize the importance of sustainability, few implement practical measures to ensure their tools endure. There are several factors that can explain this prevalence of abandonware in geo-dashboards. Many developers rely heavily on third-party libraries or services, rendering tools nonfunctional if these services are discontinued and no maintenance or contingency plans are in place. None of the reviewed tools explicitly addressed strategies for ensuring long-term longevity. Financial pressures and data privacy concerns further exacerbate these challenges; for instance, high server costs often force developers to discontinue tools. Overcoming these obstacles would require a commitment to sustainable practices, including robust maintenance strategies and proactive planning for long-term accessibility, which are difficult to realize in the current funding and reward structure of academia.

2.2. Stakeholder Engagement

Our literature review also identified *stakeholder engagement* - who is engaged, how, and how much - as a critical yet underexplored element in tool-building. We investigated each tool-building case to determine whether and in which stage stakeholders were engaged. If engagement was present, we documented the role of stakeholders, the objectives of their involvement, and the specific forms of engagement used. To understand how stakeholder engagement is used in geo-dashboard projects, we first determine the specific approach that tools used during the three key phases: as input at the start of the process, during the development process, and as evaluation and feedback at the end.

Despite its potential benefits, some form of stakeholder engagement was used in only 38 (46%) of the tool-building cases. Generally, we found that stakeholder engagement at the end of the process (53%) is more popular than at the start of the process (32%) or during the development process (45%). At this final stage, engagement often takes the form of usability testing with stakeholders, aimed at demonstrating the effectiveness of the geo-dashboards, but it rarely leads to iterative improvements to the tool. This represents a missed opportunity to build better, more impactful tools, especially given that the value of such projects ultimately lies in their use by practitioners and researchers.

When looking at the type of domain a geo-dashboard is used in, planning support systems (PSSs) place the most significant emphasis on stakeholder engagement. Among the 13 PSSs reviewed, 10 (77%) incorporated stakeholder engagement into their development processes, illustrating how the importance of stakeholder engagement is particularly present within this sub-discipline and forming a potential source of inspiration for other geo-dashboard applications.

3. Best Practices and Agenda for the Future

Based on our analysis of the current state-of-the-art, we identify several potential pathways to break build more sustainable and impactful geo-dashboards. First, stakeholder engagement requires a more structured and proactive approach. Our review highlights that effective stakeholder engagement is often underutilized, yet it plays a critical role in ensuring the usability and utility of tools. This process should begin by identifying key stakeholders and clearly defining their roles and objectives at the initial stage of project. Stakeholder engagement should not be relegated to the final stages of development, as late-stage involvement limits opportunities for meaningful contributions. Instead, engagement must be integrated across all phases of the development lifecycle, with specific engagement methods (e.g. workshops, interviews, surveys) evolving to align with the specific needs of each stage.

Second, proactively planning for accessibility and longevity is essential for preventing abandonware and ensuring sustainable tools. Our analysis revealed that many tools do not yet address these aspects adequately, often leading to obsolescence. Open-source code and licensing alone does not guarantee reusability or maintainability; these are baseline standards, not comprehensive solutions. To address these challenges, accessibility and longevity must be considered core objectives from the outset. Implementing a well-structured codebase, providing detailed documentation, and planning for long-term maintenance are critical steps during development. Developers should actively engage the research community for feedback and support, enabling broader adoption and collaboration. While third-party libraries and services can enhance sustainability, developers should also evaluate the longer-term reliability of these dependencies. Modular design, leveraging open-source alternatives, and building community-based support can further mitigate risks and safeguard tool longevity.

Finally, the ultimate goal of tool-building should be to create a meaningful impact, whether in academia, the real world, or both. Our review highlights that this goal is often overlooked, as demonstrated by the prevalence of abandonware. Creating impactful and sustainable tools requires deliberate planning and consistent effort. Developers of geo-dashboards can more explicitly prioritize impact as a guiding principle throughout all phases of development. This includes ensuring usability and utility through effective stakeholder engagement, robust technical design, and a stronger emphasis on longevity of the project. By embedding these practices into the development process, geo-dashboards can achieve their full potential, advancing research and delivering tangible benefits to broader audiences.

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